

Pythagorean fuzzy sets: a new perspective on IUP-algebras

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Abstract

Zadeh introduced the concept of fuzzy sets in 1965. In 1986, Atanassov introduced intuitionistic fuzzy sets, a generalization of fuzzy sets. Pythagorean fuzzy sets are a recent extension of intuitionistic fuzzy sets introduced by Yager. The aim of this study is to apply the concept of Pythagorean fuzzy sets to IUP-algebras and introduce the notions of Pythagorean fuzzy IUP-subalgebras, Pythagorean fuzzy IUP-ideals, Pythagorean fuzzy IUP-filters, and Pythagorean fuzzy strong IUP-ideals. Their properties are investigated, and the characteristic Pythagorean fuzzy sets, the upper t -(strong) level subsets, and the lower t -(strong) level subsets of the Pythagorean fuzzy set are studied.

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Keywords: IUP-algebra, Pythagorean fuzzy set, Pythagorean fuzzy IUP-subalgebra, Pythagorean fuzzy IUP-ideal, Pythagorean fuzzy IUP-filter, Pythagorean fuzzy strong IUP-ideal, upper t -(strong) level subset, lower t -(strong) level subset.

1 Introduction

Zadeh [15] commenced the concept of fuzzy sets (FSs) in 1965, an important concept. After that, Atanassov [1] introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs) in 1986, which is a generalization of fuzzy sets. Pythagorean fuzzy sets (PFSs) are a recent extension of IFSs. They arise when the sum of the membership level and non-membership level exceeds 1, but the sum of their squares is less than or equal to 1. For instance, Yager [14] describes a scenario where someone expresses a preference for an option x_i in criterion C_j , and the level at which

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